

A STUDY ON ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN RELATION TO GENDER AND TYPE OF SCHOOL

S. Sheela* & Dr. M. Muthamizhselvan**

* Ph.D Research Scholar (Full Time), Department of Pedagogical Sciences, Tamil Nadu Teachers Education University, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India

** Assistant Professor, Department of Pedagogical Sciences, Tamil Nadu Teachers Education University, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India

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Abstract:

Several demanding factors relating to student and family needs, as well as external evaluative processes of students' learning and process outcomes, such as abilities in planning training courses and a learning environment, are present in the school context. However, tools that adequately support schools in making self-assessment and evaluations of internal organizational climate among higher secondary school teachers are needed. Hence, the researcher has selected the problem of "A Study on Organizational Climate of Higher Secondary School Teachers" the major objectives of the study is to find out the difference between Genders: (i) Male and (ii) Female; Type of school: (i) Govt., (ii) Aided and (iii) Private schools. The samples of the study consist of 50 Higher Secondary Schoolteachers in Chennai. Data were collected through a validated tool which constructed by the researcher with the help of the Research Supervisor namely Organizational Climate (OC). The collected data were analyzed by SD, t-Test, and One way ANOVA. The findings of the study revealed that there is no significant difference between Higher Secondary School Teachers based on Gender and Type of School. The result of the study revealed that the levels of Organizational Climate of Higher Secondary School Teachers are moderate in nature.

Key Words: Organizational Climate, Higher Secondary School, Gender, Type of School, Etc...

Introduction:

The development of a nation is primarily dependent on the education system that exists in the country. Education would be meaningless without teachers playing a critical role in ensuring achievement in a learning environment. The job performance of teachers is critical to the learning process of students. Schools have had to adapt and meet new demands from society, as well as students and their parents, in recent years. Teachers' activities and roles are becoming increasingly differentiated, frequently updated, and "sophisticated," particularly in the management of their interactions with students. As a result, research on teachers' well-being has largely focused on stress and frustrations related to organizational climate, as well as relationships with colleagues and students and their families. Research has also shown that teacher well-being can be an important determinant of student learning outcomes and well-being, emphasizing the importance of identifying not only the determinants of negative outcomes for teachers, but also those of positive outcomes associated with their work.

Statement of the Problem:

The statement of the problem is entitled "A Study on Organizational Climate of Higher Secondary Schoolteachers in Relation to Gender and Type of School"

Objectives:

- To find out the level of Organizational Climate of Higher Secondary Schoolteachers.
- To compare Organizational Climate of Higher Secondary Schoolteachers based on their Gender.
- To compare Organizational Climate of Higher Secondary Schoolteachers based on the type of school.

Hypothesis:

- There is no significant difference in Organizational Climate between Male and Female Gender of Higher Secondary Schoolteachers.
- There is no significant difference in Organizational Climate of Higher Secondary Schoolteachers based on the type of school.

Need and Significance:

Teachers are arguably the most important group of professionals for the future of our country. Education would be impossible without teachers. The system will be rendered inoperable. The elevated significance is in teacher job performance. It is now more important than ever to identify the factors that have an impact job performance of a teacher in recent times, the effects of organizational climate on the years, the performance of teachers has become a hot topic. Hence the level of Organizational Climate of the teacher should be peaceful in the school circumstances ever. Therefore, the problem of the study is to investigate the Organizational Climate in relation to the respective demographic variables such as Gender, Type of the school of the higher secondary schoolteachers.

Operational Definition:

Education integrates modes of teaching delivery and assessment efforts designed to evaluate mastery of learning by students through their demonstration of the knowledge, attitudes, values, skills and behaviors required for the degree sought. Teaching competencies includes the acquisition and demonstration of the composite skills required for student’s teaching like introducing a lesson, fluency in questioning, probing questions, explaining, pace of lesson, reinforcement, understanding child psychology, recognizing behavior, classroom management. Therefore, the stakeholders, ministry of education and schools should have policy and long term periodical program to upgrade the Organizational Climate of teachers.

Higher Secondary School Teachers:

The Higher Secondary Schoolteachers are those who have completed their study in Post Graduate with B.Ed., in any recognized teacher education institutions.

Methodology:

The present study was aimed to find out Organizational Climate (OC) of Higher Secondary Schoolteachers in Chennai, for which descriptive survey method was adopted.

Population and Sample:

The population of the study was the higher secondary school teachers were randomly selected. The sample consists of 50 the higher secondary school teachers from various subjects such as science, social science and humanities in Chennai.

Delimitation of the Study:

- The data was collected in Chennai city only.
- The study has been restricted only with the demographic variables such as Gender, Type of School.

Tools Used:

Organizational Climate (OC) tool was self-constructed and validated by the researcher with the help of research supervisor.

Statistical Techniques:

The statistical techniques both descriptive analyses such as mean, standard deviation and differential analysis t-test, and One way ANOVA was employed.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Objective 1: The level of Organizational Climate of Higher Secondary School Teachers.

Table: 1 Level of Higher Secondary School Teachers

Variable	Level	N	Percentage
Organizational Climate	Low	17	34%
	Moderate	23	46%
	High	10	20%

Table 1 show that 34%, 46%, 20% of the samples have Low, Moderate, High levels of Organizational Climate of Higher Secondary School Teachers. Based on the results, it can be concluded the level of the majority of higher secondary school teachers are moderate in nature (46%).

Figure 1: Level of Organizational Climate of Higher Secondary School Teachers

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in Organizational Climate between Male and Female Gender of Higher Secondary School teachers in the study.

Table 2: Organizational Climate and It’s based on Gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-test	P-value
Male	22	125.32	4.745	0.502	0.618 ^{NS}
Female	28	124.64	4.700		

Note: * - Significant at 0.05 levels
 ** - Significant at 0.01 levels
 NS – Not Significant

Mean scores of Gender Male, and Female of higher secondary school teachers are 125.32 and 124.64 with the respective standard deviations are 4.745 and 4.700. The calculated p-value is 0.618 which is >0.05 levels and it is statistically not significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. So, “There is no significant difference in between male and female of higher secondary school teachers.

Figure 2: Difference between Male and Female of higher secondary school teachers in Organizational Climate

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in Organizational Climate of Higher Secondary School Teachers based on Type of School.

Table 3: Difference between Govt. Aided and Private of higher secondary school teachers in Organizational Climate

Location of School	N	Mean	SD	F-value	P-value
Govt.	13	122.46	5.410	2.650	0.81 ^{NS}
Aided	16	126.00	4.336		
Private	21	125.67	4.078		

Note: * - Significant at 0.05 levels
 ** - Significant at 0.01 levels
 NS – Not Significant

Mean scores of location of school, Govt., Aided and private of higher secondary school teachers are 122.46, 126.00 and 125.67 with the respective standard deviations are 5.410, 4.336 and 4.078. The calculated p-value is 0.81 which is >0.05 levels and it is statistically not significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. So, “There is no significant difference in Organizational Climate between Govt., Aided and Private of higher secondary school teachers.

Figure 3: Difference between Govt., Aided and private of higher secondary school teachers in Organizational Climate

Major Findings:

- The levels of Organizational Climate of Higher Secondary School Teachers are moderate in nature.
- There is no significant difference in Organizational Climate between Male and Female Gender of Higher Secondary School Teachers.
- There is no significant difference in Organizational Climate of the Higher Secondary School Teachers based on Type of School.

Educational Implication:

- The study will help the teachers to take care of the development of Organizational Climate for efficient teaching-learning process.
- It will help the teachers to provide necessary facilitations in the school campus.
- It will help to plan well defined, integration of Organizational Climate with different levels in teaching-learning.

Suggestions:

- The present study was conducted in Chennai, which can be extended considering population at another place.
- It was evaluating Organizational Climate of 50 Higher Secondary School Teachers, which can be extended to large no of samples.
- It was conducted on Higher Secondary School Teachers, further can be conducted the elementary teachers, high school teachers, college teachers, and vocational teachers.
- Influence of Organizational Climate with reference to other variables can be studied.

Conclusion:

The present study revealed that the level of Organizational Climate of Higher Secondary Schoolteachers is moderate in nature. The findings revealed that most of teachers in a secondary school in the Chennai underperformed in their tasks and organizational climate dimensions such as thrust and hindrance were found as crucial factors in enhancing teachers' job performance. The training could possibly focus on key leadership behaviors that promote health. The climate in the workplace According to the findings demonstrated that organizational climate was a factor critical factor in improving teachers' jobs performance, the institution's head may be able to create a committee that will be held accountable for evaluating the organizational climate among teachers.

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